

Social Entrepreneurship Development: Assessing the Role of Social Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy and Effect of Government Regulations as Moderator

Dr. Ramesh Kumar

Assistant Professor, Department of Management Studies,
Shaheed Sukhdev College of Business Studies, University of Delhi, Delhi, India

Dr. Rakesh Kumar

Professor in Commerce, Shaheed Bhagat Singh College,
University of Delhi, Delhi, India

Dr. Purushottam Bung

Professor and Director, R V Institute of Management, Bangalore, India

Shahid Amin

Associate Professor, SOM, ITM-University Gwalior, M.P., India

ABSTRACT

The principal aims of the research were to evaluate the impact of government regulations and Self Efficacy as a moderator on the development of social entrepreneurship. 459 respondents from Delhi-NCR filled out the questionnaire correctly that collected the data for further analysis. The technique employed in this study to gather information from a sample of 459 respondents was purposeful sampling. The three main methods for evaluating a research tool are validity and reliability testing, multiple linear regression testing, and hypothesis testing, which includes the t-test, F-test, and coefficient of determination tests. The results demonstrated that the two most significant variables impacting the development of social entrepreneurship are emotional intelligence and social innovation.

Keywords: *Emotional Intelligence, Creativity, Moral Obligation, Social Mission, Social Innovation, Social Entrepreneurship Development, Self Efficacy, Effect of Government Regulations*

1. INTRODUCTION

Any country's ability to create money, jobs, and economic progress is largely dependent on its entrepreneurial spirit (Akter et al., 2020;). A number of nations prioritize augmenting entrepreneurial endeavors in order to bolster economic and financial progress (Javed al., 2019). The phrase "social entrepreneurship" is enlightening and gaining popularity in its areas of advancement, yet it might be novel in the context of wealthy nations (Saebi et al., 2019). Even in times of epidemics, social entrepreneurship plays a crucial function within the company education surroundings as well as advances societal well-being (Littlewood et. al., 2018). Social entrepreneurship generates social and financial values (Alvord et al., 2004). The function social entrepreneurship highlights the unresolved societal concerns on a global scale, promotes worldwide human growth and increases life expectancy (Alarifi et al., 2019). Previous studies have acknowledged the efficiency the use of social entrepreneurship to combat poverty and unemployment, improving the environment, and enhancing human resources worldwide (Wu & Si, 2018). Previous studies have urged social entrepreneurs to draw attention to societal problems and provide solutions where they are more prevalent (Booth et al., 2019).

This study's gap is that it takes a distinct viewpoint. Researchers have highlighted a number of social entrepreneurship-related factors (Bandyopadhyay& Ray, 2019). Previous Studies have indicated that social media is a factor in the establishment of sustainable enterprises (Edgeman&Eskildsen, 2012). In the interim, Javed et al. (2019) claimed that the development of sustainable enterprises is positively and significantly impacted by social innovation, missionary work, and finances success. But prior research largely disregarded the influence of social entrepreneurship as a distinct term with a special method of administering the companies and their impact on the growth of enterprises (Roy &Karna, 2015).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Social Entrepreneurship

Individuals, groups, and start-up businesses use social entrepreneurship as a strategy to establish, fund, and place problem-solving strategies into action pertaining to the economy, environment, politics, society, and

culture (Rawhouser et al., 2019). The commercialization of the environment, which creates global economies, solves social issues, and makes use of resources, is also known as social entrepreneurship (Ashraf et al., 2019). Social entrepreneurship is a process of societal duty that uses resources to be combined and creative ideas to assist society grow both values in society and economy (Rey-Martí et al., 2016). As stated by earlier research, social entrepreneurship has become a crucial topic of study for those studying entrepreneurship and the growth of sustainable enterprises (Ali et al., 2019). As stated by Ferreira et al. (2017), Social entrepreneurship has a shared past with fostering social and economic ideals in both individuals and communities. An organization in the communal economy is also recognized as a social entrepreneurship. Governments and other organizations, however, have even increased their support of social enterprises in recent decades in an effort to manage societal issues from a variety of threats and generate employment. As indicated by Steinerowski and Steinerowska-Streb (2012), Positive systemic change combined with other entrepreneurial resources is what social enterprise is all about. It provides a cutting-edge, more socially and practically acceptable organization.

2.2 Social Entrepreneurship Development (Sed)

Due to the perceived societal benefits, entrepreneurship has grown in popularity. Creative solutions for issues within the domains of fair trade, the environment, and education nutrition, and civil liberties are the essence of social entrepreneurship (SE). While entrepreneurial initiatives are not new, they have recently attracted more attention from academics despite their goal of developing social and economic benefits (Chandra, & Kerlin, 2020). Even so, our understanding of the mechanics and problems pertaining to SE remains essentially limited. Dees (2007) points out that, in light of the present curiosity about social entrepreneurship, human history viewed as a sequence of social organization experiments that aim to answer the question of how humans can arrange themselves to become nearer to the principles of a decent society. For the most part, government has represented optimism in the effort to solve societal problems even though a civilization that blends religion and secularism has continued to emerge over time and support efforts by the government to confront poverty. In the past, government intervention to alleviate social problems has produced some noteworthy achievements, like greater access to healthcare and education. It has, nevertheless, not been without constraints.

2.3 Emotional Intelligence

The phrase "When emotional intelligence" was first published, well-known by Thorndike in 1920s as soon as he saw the connection between the notion of social intellect and emotional intelligence. Emotional intelligence, according to Thorndike, is a person's capacity to responsibly control their sentiments and emotions (Thorndike, 1937). Afterwards, Gardner (Gardner 2004) conducted investigation and developed the Multiple Intelligence Theory, which is based on seven intelligence domains (Gardner 2004). Numerous researchers from the fields of psychology and sociology are interested in this subject. Two schools of thought exist on the concept of emotional intellect. The initial one is based on psychological capacity models (Salovey and Mayer 1990). Moreover, the secondly, a hybrid strategy (Gardner 2004). Emotions and cognitive intelligence serve as the foundation for the Emotional intelligence ability model. The fundamental premise behind this is that people will be able to identify those who possess emotional self-control (Salovey and Mayer 1990). Models of emotional quotient, as characterized by mental ability, are those that deal with emotions and the distribution of emotional information (Mayer et al. 2014). In contrast, the combined model's definition of emotional intelligence includes a variety of character traits, such as a drive for success and adaptability, which enable people to better control their emotions and interpersonal interactions (Boren 2010).

H1: Emotional intelligence has significant positive impact on social entrepreneurship development (SED).

2.4 Creativity

Generally speaking, creativity is the process of producing something novel and worthwhile. The ability to combine or adapt preexisting concepts to generate new ideas or products is what makes someone creative, not the ability to create something out of nothing (Plucker et al. 2004). Innovation and creativity go together hand in hand and are regarded as the foundation of business growth (YarHamidi et al. 2008). In contrast to those who are not business owners, entrepreneurs have a conceptual structure that inspires them to "think outside the box" and generate creative answers (Sternberg et al. 2004). In a comparable manner Baron (2004) emphasized the idea that, when it comes to spotting opportunities, entrepreneurs should be more inventive than other people. Using the phrase, Schumpeter "creative destruction" To provide a definition for the phenomenon of entrepreneurship (Schumpeter 1942). Consequently, one of the most crucial components for the establishment of entrepreneurial intention is creativity. Scholars such as Gorman et al. (Gorman et al.

1997), (Feldman and Bolino 2000) and (YarHamidi et al. 2008) discovered that the process of forming intentions is positively impacted by high creativity scores. (Zampetakis et al. 2009, Zampetakis 2011). Their investigation shown that originality influences not just the procedure of intention but also the attitude toward pursuing entrepreneurship as a profession.

H2: Creativity has significant impact on social entrepreneurship development (SED).

2.5 Moral Obligation

Moral obligation might signify several things. Although moral duty is a metaphysical commitment, it is ultimately expected to result in action or change of some kind. Generally speaking, moral duty is the propensity to assist others while abiding by one's religious principles (Bryant 2009). Originally, Fishbein predicted intents using the moral component, perspective regarding behavior, as well as arbitrary standards (Fishbein 1967). How much social entrepreneurs feel morally obligated to pursue their concepts and are wholly devoted in their eyes determines their moral duty in respect to them (Beugré 2016).

In their suggested social entrepreneurship model of intention, Mair and Noboa first employed moral duty (Mair & Noboa 2006). According to their research, the Moral duty is the primary component that sets social entrepreneurs apart from business entrepreneurs. According to researchers like Dave Roberts, social entrepreneurs ought to be morally upright people (Roberts and Woods 2000). While (Hendry 2004) developed The "bi-morality" of the civilization" viewpoint, which holds that "There are two opposing sets of rules that govern our lives." Some people are driven primarily by a feeling of obligation to the community. Similar to this, social entrepreneurs are simply regular people motivated by the need to make a positive distinction between the community and the advancement of the country as a whole (Thompson 2008). (Boschee 1995) stated that those with balance are the social entrepreneurs "Moral obligations and the desire for profit" (Boschee 1995).

H3: Moral obligation has significant impact on social entrepreneurship development (SED).

2.6 Social Mission

Creating a nonprofit organization with the intention of implementing societal customs is known as a social mission (Landrum & Edwards, 2009). Social organizations operate within the constraints of making a profit and engaging in charitable endeavors (Salman & Jamil, 2017). Profit-oriented ventures are consistent the relationship between sustainable enterprise growth and social enterprises (Beckmann et al., 2014). A remarkable feature The goal of social justice is connected to social entrepreneurship, the goal of a vigorous and energetic purpose. A vague societal purpose would cause issues for social companies and lower their profitability percentage (Felício et al., 2013).

Sustainable businesses need a social mission to function well and possess a favorable social influence on the advancement of society (Fortier & Viens, 2018). Social companies can have many goals and must demonstrate their business viability and social impact. Social enterprises need to address all pertinent practices related to the social, cultural, and financial facets of the social entrepreneurial purpose in order to achieve development of sustainable enterprises.

Additionally, the social mission provides a practical means of establishing connections with the outside world while ensuring the safety and well-being of individuals within amid a natural calamity scenarios (Sonnenwald & Pierce, 2000). The societal purpose offers a practical path toward achieving sustainable business growth without endangering the environment (Kolk & van Tulder, 2010).

H4: Social mission has significant impact on social entrepreneurship development (SED).

2.7 Social Innovation

New social norms that better satisfy societal requirements and preferences than the ones that are currently in place are referred to as social innovations (Pol & Ville, 2009). It is also connected to the procedure of developing new goods, services as well as technological innovations to address various environmental problems and societal demands (Weerawardena et al., 2006). To address societal issues and provide outcomes that are beneficial to society, social innovation is essential (Sharma, 2017).

The social, environmental, and economic challenges are handled with the help of social innovation obstacles that businesses encounter while attending to the vital needs of the community in times of tragedy (Betts et al., 2018). Additionally, Social entrepreneurship seeks to develop innovative and inventive approaches to the growth of sustainable enterprises, and social innovation aids businesses in accomplishing their social innovation goals by generating novel value and developing inventive products and procedures (Guclu et al., 2002). Social creativity drives the expansion of environmentally friendly companies and meets social requirements without endangering the surroundings (Baker & Mehmood, 2015). As a result, businesses that seek to innovate socially are more prone to produce both social and economic values.

H5: Social innovation has significant impact on social entrepreneurship development(SED).

2.8 Self-Efficacy

Bandura (1977) "Self-efficacy" was defined as the source of someone's capacity to carry out a job and finish a particular activity. It has to do with how self-motivated actions, behaviors, perceptions, cognition, and surroundings interact with one another (Shahab et al., 2019). People's views about their capacities to perform at expected levels and to influence events that have an impact on their life are another definition of self-efficacy (Bandura, 1994). The range of possibilities to be evaluated is defined by the perceived self-efficacy, which also influences other aspects of decision-making. Making decisions does not guarantee that the required actions will be carried out effectively; for this reason, Self-efficacy is associated with views about one's capacity for action, while expectations of results represent the potential outcomes of one's actions (Shahab et al., 2019).

According to this viewpoint, the self-assurance of entrepreneurs can encompass both control beliefs, which suggest the capacity to control one's thoughts, both positive and negative, while pursuing goals, and objective beliefs, which indicate the capacity to judge whether a person can successfully engage in activities (Drnovšek et al., 2010). Moreover, people's perceptions of their own efficacy affect the kinds of scenarios they can see, create, and manage. Effective people study success stories because they provide constructive direction and encouragement for their work (Bandura, 1993). Put differently, self efficacy might be viewed as a type of work-specific assurance(Shane et al., 2003). This method demonstrates the substantial link that exists between behavior and self-efficacy, with human behavior being greatly impacted by conviction in one's capacity to perform the collection of actions required for success (Engle et al., 2010).

H6:Social entrepreneurship is significantly impacted by entrepreneurial self-efficacy. Development(SED).

2.9 The Moderating Role Of Self-Efficacy (Se) In Social Entrepreneurship Development

The concept of ESE stems from a more expansive understanding Having confidence in oneself, which is grounded on hypothesis of social cognition (Bandura, 1977b). This idea emphasizes the significance within a social environment, behavior Self-efficacy beliefs are developed through social learning through observation and replication. Numerous studies exist (Doanh, al, 2021) examining the connections between EI, EA, and entrepreneurial self-assurance. Few studies, however, have examined the moderating Self-efficacy's impact in entrepreneurship regarding the academic setting and curriculum learning, and intentions and mindsets of entrepreneurs, additionally to the connections between these factors and the self-efficacy of entrepreneurs.

The Doanh study in the Vietnamese setting shows showed the connection between self-efficacy in entrepreneurship and attitude and purpose in addition to having an impact on it (Doanh, 2021). Because Researchers and educators can use Self-efficacy as a means to forecast decision and output gain an improved comprehension of the connection between homework and instruction regarding the one hand, and students' opinions of individually on the other. The investigation conducted by Mozahem and Adlouni (2021)shown that, at the very least across the quartet of universities where the example was drawn, students who had completed the training had more more self-efficaciousness than those who had not. This shows how Students' future entrepreneurial aspirations are moderated by their level of self-efficacy in entrepreneurship. attitudes and intents as well as the university environment. Through entrepreneurial education, pupils' deliberate convictions and confidence in their skills to achieve, make efforts, and show perseverance in the face of difficulty are encouraged (Passaro et al., 2018).

H7:The association between is positively moderated by entrepreneurial self-efficacy. **Emotional intelligence** and social entrepreneurship development (SED).

H8:Entrepreneurial Confidence favorably moderate the connection between social entrepreneurship and creativity. Development(SED).

H9:Self-efficacy in entrepreneurship has a positive moderating effect on the association between moral obligation and social entrepreneurship development(SED).

H10:Entrepreneurial A positive moderator of the association between social mission and social entrepreneurship development(SED).

H11:Entrepreneurial Self-efficacy positively moderate the connection between the growth of social entrepreneurship and social innovation(SED).

2.10 Moderating Role of Government Regulations in Social Entrepreneurship Development

Prior research has indicated that government rules play a favorable influence in promoting creation of sustainable enterprises in nations (Lamoureux et al., 2019). The previous study looked at how government rules affected the relationship between the development of entrepreneurship and firm start-up (Li, Ahmed, et al., 2020). The results imply that governmental restrictions on business ownership have a major regulating

impact on the growth of entrepreneurship. As mentioned by Smallbone et al. (2010), Governments have a part of social entrepreneurship, assisting people in creating a social network that will support their businesses. Businesses might experience a range of productivity problems as a result of unpredictable environmental conditions. To assist these businesses, governments offer essential services like tax refunds. Additionally, van Stel et al. (2007) examined the connection between business ownership and laws in 41 different nations and discovered that a minimum amount of cash is required to launch a new company and ensure the sustainability of the operation. Consequently, laws and policies from the government play a vital part in promoting business-related social entrepreneurship and other initiatives necessary for the expansion of sustainable businesses (Oni, 2012).

H12:Government regulation has significant impact on social entrepreneurship development(SED).

H13: Government regulation has a positive moderating effect on the link between **Emotional intelligence** and social entrepreneurship development(SED).

H14:The association between creativity and government regulation is positively moderated by its effect.social entrepreneurship development(SED).

H15:The link between is positively moderated by the effect of government regulation. **Moral obligation** and social entrepreneurship development(SED).

H16:The link between government regulation and its effect is favorably moderated. **Social mission** and social entrepreneurship development(SED).

H17:The link between social innovation and government regulation is positively moderated by its effect. social entrepreneurship development(SED).

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To determine the variables impacting social entrepreneurship development (SED)
- To suggest a conceptual framework. showing the relationship of factors influencing social entrepreneurship development (SED) and moderating impact of self-efficacy and Government Regulations between selected influencing variables and social entrepreneurship development
- To validate the proposed conceptual model through empirical analysis

4. CONCEPTUAL MODEL

Emotional Intelligence (EMIN), Creativity (CRE), Moral Obligation (MOB), Development of Social Entrepreneurship, Social Innovation, and Social Mission (SOM) (SED), Self-Efficacy (SEF), and Effect of Government Regulations (EOGR) are among the influencing and dependent factors that are included in the proposed model (Figure 1). We measured each element according to the standards outlined in this investigation. This study looks at the function of Self-efficacy in social entrepreneurship and the impact of government laws as moderators in social entrepreneurship development, even if it seems logical to assume a relationship between all the variables.

Figure1: conceptual model showing the relationship of factors influencing social entrepreneurship development (SED) and moderating impact of self-efficacy and Government Regulations between selected influencing variables and social entrepreneurship development.

5. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The sampling technique used in this investigation to get a presumably representative sampling of the population is called purposeful sampling. People make up the study's sample, especially Indian business owners. The study's goal is to examine the several elements that affect Indian entrepreneurs' pursuit of business ventures, as well as the moderating influence of self-efficacy and governmental laws on the development of entrepreneurship. For the representative samples, there are about 459 respondents in total. Surveys conducted both offline and online were employed in order to gather information for this study. A Likert index scale questionnaire, with scores ranging from 1 to 5, was used in the study. For our analysis, we used IBM SPSS Statistics v.20. Factor analysis, regression analysis, test hypotheses, and Cronbach's alpha were utilized to determine the correctness of the suggested model and its dependability concept statements.

6. RESULTS

6.1 Demographic Profile

Descriptive demographic statistics were used to assess the demographic characteristics of the responder. Between March 2023 and February 2024, information was obtained by means of an extensive survey. Ultimately, it was found that 459 of the 550 questionnaires that were sent to respondents were completed and error-free. After additional verification, 83.45% of the responses are deemed to be of good quality. Each person's socio-demographic details are displayed in Table 1. males (381, 83%) outnumbered women (78, 17%) among the 459 respondents; most males (137, 29.8%) were in their 30s and 40s; 196 (42.7%) had a professional degree; 240 (52.3%) had 11 to 20 years of work experience; and 167, 36.4% made more than 30,000 rupees.

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics of Demographic Profile

	459	Frequency	Valid %
Gender profile	Male	381	83
	Female	78	17
Age profile	20-29 years	64	13.9
	30-39 years	137	29.8
	40-49 years	89	19.4
	50-59 years	102	22.2
	60 years and above	67	14.6
Highest education level	Bachelor Degree	59	12.9
	Masters Degree	112	24.4
	Professional Education	196	42.7
	Other	92	20
Working experience in years (total)	Less than 10	134	29.2
	11 to 20	240	52.3
	21 to 30	78	17
	31 to 40	7	1.5
Income	10,000- 20,000	103	22.4
	20,001- 30,000	158	34.4
	30,001- 40,000	167	36.4
	More than 40,000	31	6.8

6.2 Exploratory Factor and Reliability Analysis

The EFA was used to evaluate the conforming components' significance. In this experiment, a factor loading of 0.50 serves as the threshold. These findings imply that factor analysis is an appropriate method to gather this information. Any element with factor loadings more than 0.5 was considered in the ultimate analysis. In general, a scale is considered internally consistent if it meets the Chronbach's Alpha level is 0.70. A Cronbach's alpha level of 0.7 was used in this study.

Table 2. Results of Exploratory Factor Analysis

Variable	Cronbach alpha	Statement	Factor loadings	KMO Measure of Sample Adequacy (>0.5)	Bartlett's Test of Sphericity		Items confirmed	Items dropped	Cum % of loading
					Chi Square	Sig. (<.10)			

Emotional Intelligence (EMIN)	0.952	EMIN-1	0.210	0.840	1983.345	0.000	4	1	70.712
		EMIN-2	0.923						
		EMIN-3	0.941						
		EMIN-4	0.950						
		EMIN-5	0.923						
Creativity (CRE)	0.893	CRE-1	0.866	0.820	1486.178	0.000	5	0	70.140
		CRE-2	0.895						
		CRE-3	0.889						
		CRE-4	0.812						
		CRE-5	0.711						
Moral Obligation (MOB)	0.849	MOB-1	0.652	0.687	1109.613	0.000	4	0	69.063
		MOB-2	0.877						
		MOB-3	0.940						
		MOB-4	0.828						
Social Mission (SOM)	0.952	SOM-1	0.225	0.848	1983.730	0.000	4	1	70.804
		SOM-2	0.926						
		SOM-3	0.942						
		SOM-4	0.953						
		SOM-5	0.915						
Social Innovation (SOIN)	0.707	SOIN-1	0.627	0.722	340.775	0.000	4	1	43.114
		SOIN-2	0.788						
		SOIN-3	0.785						
		SOIN-4	0.187						
		SOIN-5	0.701						
Social Entrepreneurship Development (SED)	0.954	SED-1	0.230	0.847	2013.737	0.000	4	1	71.122
		SED-2	0.925						
		SED-3	0.943						
		SED-4	0.951						
		SED-5	0.924						
Self Efficacy (SEF)	0.895	SEF-1	0.869	0.824	1508.898	0.000	5	0	70.654
		SEF-2	0.897						
		SEF-3	0.890						
		SEF-4	0.815						
		SEF-5	0.717						
Effect of Government Regulations (EOGR)	0.852	EOGR-1	0.827	0.699	1085.321	0.000	4	0	69.474
		EOGR-2	0.936						
		EOGR-3	0.877						
		EOGR-4	0.672						

6.3 Correlation Analysis

As per the findings of the independent variable correlation study, there seems to be a robust association between all the variables. Both the dependent and independent variables have a significant connection when all factors are taken into account (Table 3). The variables evaluating Social Mission (SOM) and Emotional Intelligence (EMIN) had the highest level of correlation (0.998), whereas the ones measuring Social Innovation (SOIN) and Effect of Government Regulations (EOGR) had the least significant link (0.718).

Table 3: Correlations

	EMIN	CRE	MOB	SOM	SOIN	SED	SEF	EOGR
EMIN	1							
CRE	.923**	1						
MOB	.906**	.869**	1					
SOM	.998**	.919**	.908**	1				
SOIN	.795**	.771**	.735**	.800**	1			
SED	.989**	.905**	.901**	.989**	.817**	1		

SEF	.920**	.983**	.875**	.920**	.807**	.928**	1
EOGR	.839**	.802**	.932**	.843**	.718**	.856**	.834**

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

6.4 Regression Analysis

Using stepwise Regression analysis was used to determine the relationship between the independent and dependent variables. The study's main goals were to evaluate the significance of social entrepreneurial self-efficacy and effect of government regulations as moderator in Social Entrepreneurship Development.

6.4.1 Social Entrepreneurship Development (SED) as Dependent Variable: The link between the independent and dependent variables in terms of predictors and criteria was found using stepwise regression analysis. Tables 4a and 4b, which used step-wise regression analysis, showed that the variables under investigation are highly significant predictors of the development of social entrepreneurship. Table 4a shows that these traits account for 98.2% of Social Entrepreneurship Development, with a R square of 0.982. Table 4b displays the regression model's ANOVA values, which demonstrate validation at a 95% confidence level. The beta values of all the components are 0.723 and 0.244, which accurately reflects their influence on the development of social entrepreneurship, based on the Table's coefficient summary 4c.

Table 4a: Regression analysis

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.991 ^a	.982	.982	.13447

a. Predictors: (Constant), CRE, SOIN, MOB, SOM, EMIN

Table 4b: ANOVA analysis

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	441.761	5	88.352	4886.475	.000 ^b
	Residual	8.191	453	.018		
	Total	449.951	458			

a. Dependent Variable: SED

b. Predictors: (Constant), CRE, SOIN, MOB, SOM, EMIN

Table 4c: Regression coefficients table for dependent variables

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-0.096	.027		-3.506	.001
	EMIN	0.732	0.097	0.723	7.537	.000
	CRE	-0.091	0.020	-0.080	-4.621	.000
	MOB	0.035	0.018	0.031	1.998	.046
	SOM	0.246	0.096	0.244	2.560	.011
	SOIN	0.114	0.014	0.085	7.879	.000

a. Dependent Variable: SED

6.4.2 Impact of Self Efficacy and Government Regulations on Social Entrepreneurship Development (SED):The link between the independent and dependent variables in terms of predictors and criteria was found using stepwise regression analysis. Government regulations and self-efficacy are important predictors of the growth of social entrepreneurship demonstrated by Tables 5a and 5b. Table 5a shows that these factors explain 88.4% on the growth of social entrepreneurship, with a R square of 0.884. Table 5b displays the regression model's ANOVA values, which demonstrate validation at a 95% confidence level. The beta values of all the components are 0.703 and 0.270, which accurately reflects their influence on the development of social entrepreneurship, based on the Table's coefficient summary 5c.

Table 5a: Regression analysis

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.940 ^a	.884	.883	.33885

a. Predictors: (Constant), EOGR, SEF

Table 5b: ANOVA analysis

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	397.594	2	198.797	1731.405	.000 ^b
	Residual	52.357	456	.115		
	Total	449.951	458			

a. Dependent Variable: SED

b. Predictors: (Constant), EOGR, SEF

Table 5c: Regression coefficients table for dependent variables

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-0.201	.053		-3.756	.000
	SEF	0.797	.033	.703	24.277	.000
	EOGR	0.296	0.032	0.270	9.332	.000

a. Dependent Variable: SED

6.4.3 Moderating impact of self-efficacy between selected influencing variables and social entrepreneurship development:

The Zscore values for each variable were developed to investigate the connection between self-efficacy and governmental restrictions development of social entrepreneurship. Next, by calculating the interaction between all independent factors and Government Regulations and Self-Efficacy, new variables are formed, which are represented as interactions IA1 through IA10.

Regression analysis was performed using the dependent variable (SED) and the additional interacting independent variables (IA1 through IA5). Considering the outcomes of step-wise regression analysis, Tables 6a and 6b show how these interacting traits are a strong predictor of Social Entrepreneurship Development (SED). The R square value of 0.884 in Table 6 indicates that these variables are responsible for 88.4% of the success of entrepreneurship development. Table 6b displays the regression model's ANOVA values, which demonstrate validation at a 95% confidence level. According to Table 6c's coefficient summary, the beta values are, respectively, 0.322 and 0.153. These ideals fairly reflect the ways in which they influence the development of entrepreneurship.

Table 6a: Regression analysis

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	No results were there	Pls check		

a. Predictors: (Constant), EOGR, SEF

Table 6b: ANOVA analysis

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	59.993	5	11.999	13.938	.000 ^b
	Residual	389.958	453	.861		
	Total	449.951	458			

a. Dependent Variable: SED

b. Predictors: (Constant), IA5, IA3, IA1, IA2, IA4

Table 6c: Regression coefficients table for dependent variables

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	2.552	.054		47.038	.000
IA1	0.236	0.704	0.322	0.336	.000
IA2	-0.062	0.148	-0.088	-0.419	.675
IA3	-0.064	0.123	-0.080	-0.522	.602
IA4	0.113	0.690	0.153	0.163	.000
IA5	0.039	0.072	0.056	0.541	.000

a. Dependent Variable: SED

6.4.4 Moderating impact of Government Regulations between selected influencing variables and social entrepreneurship development: Regression analysis was performed using the dependent variable (SED) and the additional interacting independent variables (IA6 to IA10). Considering the outcomes of step-wise regression analysis, Tables 7a and 7b show how these interacting traits are a strong predictor of Social Entrepreneurship Development (SED). Table 7's R square value of 0.149 indicates that 14.9% of the accomplishment of Entrepreneurship Development could be ascribed to these elements. Table 7b displays the regression model's ANOVA values, which demonstrate validation at a 95% confidence level. According to Table 7c's coefficient summary, the beta values are, respectively, 0.591 and 0.133. These ideals fairly reflect the ways in which they influence the development of entrepreneurship.

Table 7a: Regression analysis

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.386 ^a	.149	.139	.91952

a. Predictors: (Constant), IA10, IA8, IA7, IA9, IA6

Table 7b: ANOVA analysis

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	66.930	5	13.386	15.832	.000 ^b
Residual	383.021	453	.846		
Total	449.951	458			

a. Dependent Variable: SED

b. Predictors: (Constant), IA10, IA8, IA7, IA9, IA6

Table 7c: Regression coefficients table for dependent variables

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	2.533	.055		46.076	.000
IA6	.480	.384	.591	1.250	.000
IA7	-.263	.101	-.323	-2.596	.010
IA8	.047	.087	.056	.546	.000
IA9	-.068	.370	-.083	-.182	.855
IA10	.105	.063	.133	1.663	.007

a. Dependent Variable: SED

6.5 Results of Hypotheses Testing

The conceptual research framework initially proposed 17 hypotheses; table 8 shows which 14 of the hypotheses have been accepted and which three have been rejected.

Table 8: Summary of Hypotheses Testing

Hy. No.	Independent Variables	Dependent Variables	R-Square	Beta Coefficient	t-value	Sig Value	Status of Hypotheses
H1	Emotional Intelligence (EMIN)	Social Entrepreneurship Development (SED)	0.982	.723	7.537	.000	Accepted
H2	Creativity (CRE)	Social Entrepreneurship Development (SED)		-.080	-4.621	.000	Accepted
H3	Moral Obligation (MOB)	Social Entrepreneurship Development (SED)		.031	1.998	.046	Accepted
H4	Social Mission (SOM)	Social Entrepreneurship Development (SED)		.244	2.560	.011	Accepted
H5	Social Innovation (SOIN)	Social Entrepreneurship Development (SED)		.085	7.879	.000	Accepted
H6	Self Efficacy (SEF)	Social Entrepreneurship Development (SED)	0.884	.703	24.277	.000	Accepted
H7	IA1	Social Entrepreneurship Development (SED)	0.884	.322	.336	.000	Accepted
H8	IA2	Social Entrepreneurship Development (SED)		-.088	-.419	.675	Rejected
H9	IA3	Social Entrepreneurship Development (SED)		-.080	-.522	.602	Rejected
H10	IA4	Social Entrepreneurship Development (SED)		.153	.163	.000	Accepted
H11	IA5	Social Entrepreneurship Development (SED)		.056	.541	.000	Accepted
H12	Effect of Government Regulations (EOGR)	Social Entrepreneurship Development (SED)	0.884	.270	9.332	.000	Accepted
H13	IA6	Social Entrepreneurship Development (SED)	0.149	.591	1.250	.000	Accepted
H14	IA7	Social Entrepreneurship Development (SED)		-.323	-2.596	.010	Accepted
H15	IA8	Social Entrepreneurship Development (SED)		.056	.546	.000	Accepted
H16	IA9	Social Entrepreneurship Development (SED)		-.083	-.182	.855	Rejected
H17	IA10	Social Entrepreneurship Development (SED)		.133	1.663	.007	Accepted

7. DISCUSSION

Under the relationship between self-efficacy and the effect of government regulations, the study discovered a substantial favorable correlation between emotional intelligence as well as the growth of social enterprise (H1, H7, and H13). Numerous scholarly investigations have underscored the role that emotional intelligence plays in the context of stress management and emotional collapse (Tsaousis and Nikolaou, 2005) and stress management is frequently associated with a favourable outlook on entrepreneurship and entrepreneurial aspirations. Since social entrepreneurs must find innovative ways to address the unmet needs of society, emotional intelligence is also crucial to their success. Therefore, controlling and directing one's emotions and impulses can give social entrepreneurs a significant competitive advantage. Therefore, It's wise to use emotional intelligence whenever possible to forecast the intents and trajectory of social entrepreneurship.

Under the moderating influence of government regulations, rather than with self-efficacy, the empirical analysis of hypotheses 2 and 14 showed a strong correlation that favorably links creativity to the development of social entrepreneurship (H8; beta coefficient = -0.088; t-value = -0.419). Passion and creativity have an impact on the objectives and development of entrepreneurs because, in addition to passion, creativity is a necessary quality for success in business; creative people create novel approaches or creative solutions to challenges. to carry out tasks.

A robust positive association exists between the two notions, according to an independent study On the connection between Moral Duty and Social Entrepreneurship Development under the result of government regulations. The outcome aligns with Hypotheses 3 and 15, but not with H9 (t-value = -0.522; beta

coefficient = -0.080). This implies that people would look for creative ways to offer answers to the issues they encounter as they feel more and more obligated to help others who are socially disadvantaged. Governments are involved in social entrepreneurship and assist people in creating a social network that is necessary for the viability of businesses, claim Smallbone et al. (2010).

Considerably, results (hypotheses 4 and 10) show that Social Mission does, in fact, considerably boost Social Entrepreneurship Development when paired with Self Efficacy, but not when associated with Government Regulations (H16, beta coefficient = -0.083; t-value = -0.182). Consistent with the results of the earlier research (Muscat &Whitty, 2009), we found that social mission serves as a reliable indicator of the establishment of sustainable enterprises. Furthermore, a recent quantitative cross-sectional study that looked at social mission's effect on sustainable businesses' expansion discovered that social mission had a beneficial impact on this process. As a result, our research indicates that social mission has a big influence on the development of sustainable businesses, and the outcomes are discussed (Javed et al., 2019), indicating the social entrepreneurs' assistance from social enterprises in addressing social and economic problems.

As a result of self-efficacy and government regulations, the empirical research of hypothesis 5, 11, and 17 demonstrated a considerable positive relationship between social entrepreneurship and social innovation development. It was discovered that the development of sustainable enterprises was positively impacted by social creativity. Social innovation is the dynamic element of social enterprise. Melville (2010) asserts that The best indicator of economic sustainability is social innovation, and is beneficial in addressing the social, cultural, and environmental obstacles that businesses encounter. This outcome is consistent with earlier research (Aksoy et al., 2019).

A considerable positive link was found between government regulations, social entrepreneurship development, and self-efficacy after hypotheses 6 and 12 were empirically investigated. The moderating function of self-efficacy in social entrepreneurship within the social entrepreneurship area has been specifically studied in recent study by Ukil et al. (2023).

8. CONCLUSION

For scholars, social entrepreneurs, and politicians, the study offers applications. The social entrepreneurship elements that support sustainable businesses in achieving maximum profitability and shielding their operations from various environmental risks were examined in our study. According to the study, social innovation and emotional intelligence have a remarkable quality of social entrepreneurship that is connected to the goal of a strong and capable purpose. As a result, people who have Strong social mission and emotional intelligence are more likely to succeed in social organizations and contribute to the acquisition of competitive advantages. Additionally, research shows that in epidemic scenarios, social entrepreneurs use human resources, creative government or business sector-directed concepts, new product development, and expertise to create sustainable entrepreneurial solutions to address societal concerns. Social networking across companies makes social entrepreneurs more valuable to the market and gives them the ability to influence social innovation. Finally, by using social missions, creative environments, and methods that will strengthen the economy and the growth of social enterprises, Our research will assist social entrepreneurs in putting pressure on competitors in the market.

In social and unpredictable environment situations, this study attempted to evaluate the significance of social entrepreneurship aspects, emotional intelligence, Using social innovation, social mission, and inventiveness to achieve sustainable business development with government support laws. Furthermore, the best indicator for resolving all social, economic, and environmental problems is enterprise sustainability.

9. FUTURE PROSPECTS AND LIMITATIONS

There are several restrictions on this results, along with suggestions for additional research. First, in order to quantify the significance of sustainable enterprise development, we have simply measured five social entrepreneurship characteristics and two moderating indicators. Other components of social entrepreneurship, like the risk-taking, locus of control, and the urge for accomplishment can be included by future academics in their research. Second, as a moderator variable, we have included government rules and self-efficacy. Other sustainable human resource and management techniques can be used by future academics to expand on the current body of knowledge. Thirdly, our The study was cross-sectional and only used data. gathered from an online and offline survey. This methodology can be applied to longitudinal design study in the future to help more broadly generalize the findings.

This study's limitations—namely, its small sample size, geographical dispersion, and the time constraints placed on the target subjects—may diminish the generality in addition to its remarkable contributions. Therefore, it is essential to conduct an extended study project to investigate ways to improve community policies that assist entrepreneurs and propel further economic changes in India.

More time must pass for observation in this dynamic, constantly changing environment before the true behavioral patterns of entrepreneurs can be determined, given that the emergence of emerging markets in India is relatively recent—it dates back only about 20 years—and that the culture of entrepreneurship takes time to take root.

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